

Gesture Analysis and Recognition of Bow-Stringed Instruments using Motion Capture System Qualisys

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Abstract

Gesture analysis of instrumental performance has been a hot-discussed topic for a long time. Previous work mainly focus on violin performance. In this paper, we use a optical motion capture system Qualisys to capture gesture data of violin, viola and cello. For each instrument, we record 5 techniques (détaché, martelé, spiccato, staccato and staccato down) with 3 dynamics (piano, mezzo forte and forte). After calibration, bow descriptors computation and score-alignment, we use a vector of bow velocity to represent a stroke. We then categorize strokes according to their techniques, dynamics and durations. After analysis of each category, we propose five features to differentiate them. Using LIBSVM and 4-fold cross validation, we perform several classification tasks from different angles to classify them. Result shows that our method proves to be effective to differentiate strokes of different techniques with different dynamics.

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1. Introduction

As part of performance modeling, gesture analysis has been a hot discussed topic for many years. Not only because it could supervise human movements from a data point of view in order to improve performance and correct gestures. But also it is very important for gesture-based synthesis and augmented instruments. Among them, the gestural parameters of bow-stringed instruments are studied most for their rich articulations and expressiveness.

Previous gesture analysis and classification of bow-stringed instruments works mainly focus on violin performance. In [1], the CyberViolin project uses an electromagnetic motion tracking system called CAVE™ to capture raw gesture data (6DOFs of two sensors in absolute coordinate system) which is recorded in a temporary data structure until an entire bow stroke can be analyzed in real time. Based on this, some features including the velocity, change in distance between the frog and the bow, plane of the violin strings, number of stoppage, continuity, acceleration for first and middle segments, and similarity of bow usage are applied to a decision tree, to classify between five techniques (martelé, détaché, spiccato, legato, staccato). Another gesture analysis work of violin bow strokes uses two accelerometers to obtain bow accelerations. In this project, individual strokes are segmented by a peak detection algorithm[2]. They find the most effect parameters are maximum and minimum of acceleration and they apply them to a kNN method to classify between détaché, martelé and spiccato. Recently Young uses force, inertial and position sensors to capture 8 gesture data of six bow techniques with fixed length (1144 samples)[3]. Thus, an individual stroke can be represented by a 9152 (1144*8) dimension vector. Then they uses principle component analysis (PCA) to reduce the vector to three most salient features as the input of kNN for classification with three-fold cross-validation.

In this paper, compared with Askenfelt's calibrated measurement system using thin resistive wire and strain gauges [4] and previous music technology group's 3D tracking system based on electro-magnetic field (EMF) sensing [5], we use a commercial optical motion capture system called Qualisys to capture gesture data. This system is similar to the one in [6] but more accurate and enables us to analyze gestures in a more detailed way. Our method is similar to [2]. However, we will comprehensively cover 5 techniques with 3 different dynamics and propose more features to differentiate and recognize them. Besides, apart from violin we will also analyze gestures of viola and cello, which has never been studied in previous works.

The organization of this paper is as follows. In section 2 we introduce the experiment setup of motion capture system. In section 3 we describe the necessary preprocessing of gesture data for further work. Section 4 analyze the categorized strokes of different techniques with different dynamics and several features are proposed. In section 5 we perform several classification tasks to recognise strokes. Section 6 represents the result of classification with some discussion included. In section 7 we conclude our work and describe the future work.

2. Experimental Setup

Figure 2.1: A schematic overview of motion capture system. Motions are captured by Qualisys while audios are recorded simultaneously.

The whole system is shown in figure 2.1. We use Qualisys to capture motions while recording simultaneous audios and synchronize them using SMPTE timecode later. The Qualisys is equipped with both hardware and software part and we will introduce them individually.

2.1 Hardware Design

Figure 2.2: Oqus camera and markers attached to instrumental body, bow and performers

The key hardware component in Qualisys motion capture systems is the Oqus camera. The core of the Oqus marker-based cameras is the ability to calculate marker positions with highest accuracy and speed. Hundreds of markers can be measured at thousands of frames per second with ten, fifty or even more cameras [7]. For our particular purpose, we use 28 Oqus cameras to capture reflective markers attached to instrumental body, bow and performers from different angles (see figure 2.2). We set sampling rate to 300 frames per second for most recordings and 150 frames for a few.

2.2 Qualisys Track Manager

Qualisys Track Manager, or QTM for short, is Qualisys' main software that handles the motion capture process in an efficient and user friendly way. Our operations of QTM consist of following steps: (1) collects 2D marker position data and calculates 3D and 6DOF data (figure 2.3 a). (2) manually annotate markers in a recording and build models based on them (figure 2.3 b). (3) apply models to unannotated recordings, correct markers missed or mistakenly annotated and adjust previous models. (4) interpolate markers which have inconsecutive frames due to missing or mistaken

capture. (figure 2.3 c)

We spend a whole month to finish processing all recordings. We annotate markers not only for our research topic, but also that will be important for future work such as those attached to performers.

Thus a recording is represented by an $M * 3 \times N$ matrix, where M is the number of annotated markers, N is the number of frames and 3 are the x, y and z position of a marker. We then export recordings to .tsv format, a text-based one which can be read into Matlab for further processing.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 2.3: Operations of qualisys track manager. a) transformation of 2D marker position to 3D data. b) annotating markers manually. c) interpolation of inconsecutive frames

2.3 Organization of Raw Gesture Data Acquisition

As mentioned before, a big difference between our research and previous works is that our data comprise recordings of violin, viola and cello. For each instrument, we record six different techniques: détaché, legato, martelé, spiccato, staccato and staccato down, each technique with one recording. However, some incomplete recordings are discarded and we will list them in Section 5.

The organization of all recordings is the same. For each recording, performers are asked to play diatonic scale notes from C1 to D3 (the octaves may vary according to instrument) at 3 different tempi with 3 different dynamics: piano, mezzo forte and forte. For example, a player first plays notes with piano at lowest tempo, then piano at mid tempo and piano at highest tempo and after a short pause he begins the same pattern but with mezzo forte and forte (see figure 2.4). Each note is repeated once and 8 notes are played per string. The bow direction changes every note for any technique except legato. Thus we leave all the legato recordings alone due to this difference and study only 5 other techniques.

Figure 2.4: The organization of a recording: three segments represent notes with piano, mezzo forte and forte respectively and each segment is played at from low tempo, mid tempo to high tempo.

3. Gesture Data Preprocessing

From this section and below, all the processing will be implemented in Matlab, based on the .tsv file exported from Qualisys. The preprocessing is to prepare everything ready for gesture analysis and classification. Thus we need to compute bow descriptors on a note-by-note basis.

3.1 Virtual Markers Calibration

The virtual markers in our case mean markers that are removed during recording, but are installed before so that we can calibrate their virtual positions through positions of other non virtual markers. We follow the same method in [5] but we use nine markers not sensors to build three local coordinate systems, three for each. We choose markers attached to antenna of string 1, antenna of string 4, side bottom of body for body coordinate system, markers attached to stick frog, back of antenna, front of antenna for bow frog coordinate system, markers attached to front of stick tip, middle of stick tip, back of stick tip for bow tip coordinate system because these markers are relatively more stable than others through all recordings. After computing the β coordinates of virtual markers relevant to their closest local coordinate systems, we can obtain their virtual positions referred to the original coordinate system (see figure 3.1). Thus we obtain all markers necessary for computation of bow descriptors.

Figure 3.1: The calibration of virtual marker. P_V is the virtual marker. P_1 , P_2 and P_3 are the non virtual markers defining the local coordinate system.

3.2 Bow Descriptors Computation

According to [1], the most influential bow descriptors are bow velocity, bow force, bow-bridge distance and bow position. Initially we want to mainly use bow velocity and bow force and discuss others in the future work. However, there are some problems to be solved about estimation of bow force. Therefore we decide to only use bow velocity for the moment.

The bow velocity is computed as the derivative of bow displacement. To compute the bow displacement, first a virtual string is defined by taking the averages of the heads and the bridges of string 2 and string 3 (This could avoid the abrupt change of bow velocity when jumping from one string to another). Then we define an virtual bow which are not deformed as the lines between actual bow tip markers and bow frog markers (the actual bow has markers on frog and tip of both sides). Next we find the shortest lines between the virtual string and both the left side and right side of the virtual bow. Finally the bow displacement is obtained by averaging the distances between points of lines on the bow end and their corresponding bow frogs. See figure 3.2 for details.

Thus as shown in figure 3.3, the bow velocity of a recording has been computed but not yet divided into notes. Our next step is to segment it by score alignment.

Figure 3.2: The computation of bow velocity. S_V is the virtual string between string 2 and string 3. F_L and F_R are the bow frog markers on left and right sides T_L and T_R are the bow tip markers. P_L and P_R are points of smallest lines between the virtual string and virtual bow.

Figure 3.3: The bow velocity of a recording. The x axis is the index of frames and y axis is the velocity.

3.3 Score Alignment and Performance Segmentation

To segment a whole recording into individual strokes, we choose to annotate notes manually to avoid any mistakes caused by automatic segmentation algorithm. Moreover, we use Sonic Visualizer to annotate simultaneous audio recordings and synchronize them with motion capture data using SMPTE timecode, which is more accurate than direct annotating motion capture data.

The Sonic Visualizer provides an easy tool to annotate notes by defining onsets and offsets. Besides, we can add pitch and other information as text. Once the annotation is completed, we can export it to a text file and read it into Matlab. See figure 3.4 for

details.

Figure 3.4: The annotation of simultaneous audio recordings in Sonic Visualizer

SMPTE timecode is a set of cooperating standards to label individual frames of video or film with a time code defined by the Society of Motion Picture and Television Engineers in the SMPTE 12M specification [8]. Timecodes are added to film, video or audio material, and have also been adapted to synchronize music. They provide a time reference for editing, synchronization and identification.

SMPTE timecodes contain binary coded decimal *hour:minute:second:frame* identification and 32 bits for use by users. In our case every frame of motion capture data has an identification and we use the 32 bits to store the corresponding index of frame in the simultaneous audio recordings, which establishes a connection between them. Therefore we can transform the annotation of audio recordings into annotation of motion capture data and segment the bow velocity of a whole recording on a note-by-note basis (see figure 3.5).

Thus for every recording, we segment it into separate strokes and each stroke is represented by a vector of bow velocity whose length is the number of frames it contains in motion capture data. Now everything has been prepared for our next step to analyze gestures based on strokes they comprise.

Figure 3.5: The segmented bow velocity in a recording. Each stroke is segmented by two bars.

4. Gesture Analysis and Feature Extraction

Our goal is to analyze the difference among gestures of same instrument but with different techniques and different dynamics and then to recognize them using classification method. Besides as mentioned before, notes are played at three different tempi and differ a lot from each other. Therefore for a recording in which notes have same instrument and technique, we categorize notes into nine categories as different combinations of three dynamics and three tempi, 32 notes for each. Since the techniques of one instrument are similar to those of another, we decide to focus on cello because the quality of its recordings is comparably better than viola and violin. In the following part we will plot and analyze each recording of cello separately and based on the analysis we propose several features to differentiate them. As mentioned before, the bow direction changes alternatively. Therefore we will deal with only half of the strokes which have same bow direction.

4.1 Gesture Analysis

a) Detache

The detache is the most common bow stroke in string playing. It is usually played in the middle part of the bow, with one note per stroke. Although the spelling of the term suggests a detached articulation, the bow never stops between strokes.

From figure 4.1 a we can see the bow velocity of detache reaches to its maximum at the very beginning, then drops down to zero with a flat curve.

b) Martele

The martelé is a percussive stroke produced by pinching the string with the bow before drawing the bow. In each stroke, almost all of this weight is suddenly released from the string, but only for a moment while the bow is in motion.

From figure 4.1 b we can see the bow velocity of martelé reaches to its maximum at the very end, then drops down to zero all of a sudden.

c) Spiccato

The spiccato is performed by a natural bouncing of the bow from the string in the middle portion of the bow. The exact location varies from bow to bow dependent on the location of the “bouncing point” on the stick.

From figure 4.1 c we can see the bow velocity of spiccato reaches to its maximum at the very beginning, but drops down to negative in the end compared with détaché.

d) Staccato

The staccato is used as a generic term. Staccato means a non-legato martelé type of short bow stroke played with a stop. The effect is to shorten the written note value with an unwritten rest.

From figure 4.1 d we can see the bow velocity of staccato reaches to its maximum at the very beginning, drops down to zero in the middle, holds for a while, and drops down to negative in the end.

e) Staccato down

The staccato down is a name we agreed on having for the technique in which the bow stays on the string even after the velocity has come to zero, as opposed to the case of the other staccato, in which the bow leaves the string.

From figure 4.1 e we can see the bow velocity of staccato down reaches to its maximum at the very beginning, drops down to zero in the middle and holds till the end.

f) Dynamics

As a result of observation of 5 recordings, we can see strokes with same technique but different dynamics are similar in general shape but different in amplitude.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

Figure 4.1: The categorized strokes of cello. From left to right are long, middle, short duration. From top to bottom are piano, mezzo forte, forte. a) détaché b) martelé c) spiccato d) staccato e) staccato down

4.2 Feature Extraction

Based on the previous observation and analysis, we propose five features to differentiate strokes with different techniques and dynamics, as shown in figure 4.2.

a) Max Velocity

The max velocity is the maximum of absolute velocity of a stroke.

b) Max Time

The max time is the relative time when a stroke reaches its max velocity divided by its duration.

c) Max Difference

The max difference is the difference of subtracting a stroke's maximum velocity by its minimum velocity.

d) Release Time

The release time is the relative time when a stroke drops down to 10 percent of its max velocity divided by its duration.

e) Velocity Centroid

We take a similar definition of temporal centroid in [9]. The velocity centroid is the time averaged over the velocity envelop.

$$V_c = \frac{\sum_t v(t) \cdot t}{\sum_t v(t)}$$

Figure 4.2: Features extracted from the bow velocity of a stroke

After extracting all the features from bow velocity, we can discard the whole and use only features and other properties tags (techniques, dynamics, duration, pitch ,etc) to form a new vector representing a stroke, which will be the input of classification in the following section.

5. Gesture Recognition

In this section we will classify strokes from several different aspects. We first describe the data for classification and then introduce the strategy we use.

5.1 Data Overview

For each instrument, we use a matrix to store information of all strokes, in which each row is a vector to represent a stroke mentioned in the previous section. We use features as parameters of input, and single property or combination of different properties as class tags of input to retrieve different data sets and perform different classification tasks.

Also as mentioned earlier, the martelé and spiccato of violin is discarded due to the missing of frames. Some frames of détaché of violin are also missing but acceptable.

5.2 Classification Method

We use LIBSVM for Matlab for classification [10]. LIBSVM is an integrated library for support vector classification, regression and distribution estimation. It supports multi-class classification.

The classification tasks we will perform are listed below.

a) classify between 3 dynamics for the same technique

For each instrument, we perform 5 tasks separately. We retrieve strokes with same technique and use dynamics as class tags for classification.

b) classify between 5 techniques for the same dynamics

For each instrument, we perform 3 tasks separately. We retrieve strokes with same dynamics and use techniques as class tags for classification.

c) classify between any dynamics and techniques

For each instrument, we perform 1 task only. We retrieve all strokes and use combination of techniques as class tags for classification.

d) cascade classification between any dynamics and techniques

The data and final output are same with the previous one. However, this one consists of two steps. First we retrieve all strokes but only use techniques as class tags for classification. Next based on the output of first step we put data to different classifiers and combine the output of first step and second as the final.

One important thing should be noticed is that for any task above we actually perform 3 subtasks for strokes with long, middle and short duration respectively and take the average of them as final result.

For evaluation, considering the size of our data is relatively small, we choose 4-fold cross validation, which means we randomly select three fourths of the whole for training and the rest for testing, and repeat four times to achieve final result.

6. Result and Discussion

In this section we will show the results of classification tasks and discuss them individually.

a) classify between 3 dynamics for the same technique

	<i>DE</i>	<i>ST</i>	<i>SD</i>
Avg. Acc.	82.8%	93.1%	77.4%

	<i>p</i>	<i>mf</i>	<i>f</i>
<i>p</i>	90.6%	7.3%	2.1%
<i>mf</i>	8.3%	82.3%	9.4%
<i>f</i>	1.0%	17.7%	75.1%

	<i>p</i>	<i>mf</i>	<i>f</i>
<i>p</i>	100.0%	0	0
<i>mf</i>	0	92.7	7.3%
<i>f</i>	0	13.5%	86.5%

	<i>p</i>	<i>mf</i>	<i>f</i>
<i>p</i>	93.8%	6.2%	0
<i>mf</i>	14.6%	63.5%	21.9%
<i>f</i>	0	25.0	75.0%

(a)

	<i>DE</i>	<i>MA</i>	<i>SP</i>	<i>ST</i>	<i>SD</i>
Avg. Acc.	66.7%	82.3%	86.5%	63.2%	69.1%

	<i>p</i>	<i>mf</i>	<i>f</i>
<i>p</i>	81.3%	17.7%	1.0%
<i>mf</i>	31.2%	57.3%	11.5%
<i>f</i>	1.0%	37.5%	61.5%

	<i>p</i>	<i>mf</i>	<i>f</i>
<i>p</i>	91.7%	7.3%	1.0%
<i>mf</i>	11.5%	74.0%	14.5%
<i>f</i>	0	18.7%	81.3%

	<i>p</i>	<i>mf</i>	<i>f</i>
<i>p</i>	96.9%	3.1%	0
<i>mf</i>	6.3%	76.0	17.7%
<i>f</i>	0	13.5%	86.5%

	<i>p</i>	<i>mf</i>	<i>f</i>
<i>p</i>	82.3%	13.5%	4.2%
<i>mf</i>	27.1%	43.7%	29.2%
<i>f</i>	2.1%	34.4%	63.5%

	<i>p</i>	<i>mf</i>	<i>f</i>
<i>p</i>	87.5%	4.2%	8.3%
<i>mf</i>	9.4%	58.3%	32.3%
<i>f</i>	9.4%	29.2%	61.4%

(b)

	<i>DE</i>	<i>MA</i>	<i>SP</i>	<i>ST</i>	<i>SD</i>
Avg. Acc.	85.4%	88.9%	82.6%	95.5%	99.3%

	<i>p</i>	<i>mf</i>	<i>f</i>
<i>p</i>	89.6%	10.4%	0
<i>mf</i>	10.4%	82.3%	7.3%
<i>f</i>	0	15.6%	84.4%

	<i>p</i>	<i>mf</i>	<i>f</i>
<i>p</i>	86.5%	13.5%	0
<i>mf</i>	3.1%	91.7%	5.2%
<i>f</i>	0	11.5%	88.5%

	<i>p</i>	<i>mf</i>	<i>f</i>
<i>p</i>	74.0%	25.0%	1.0%
<i>mf</i>	12.5%	82.3%	5.2%
<i>f</i>	0	8.3%	91.7%

	<i>p</i>	<i>mf</i>	<i>f</i>
<i>p</i>	95.8%	4.2%	0
<i>mf</i>	2.1%	93.7%	4.2%
<i>f</i>	1.0%	2.1%	96.9%

	<i>p</i>	<i>mf</i>	<i>f</i>
<i>p</i>	100.0%	0	0
<i>mf</i>	0	100.0%	0
<i>f</i>	0	2.1%	97.9%

(c)

Table 6.1: The average accuracies and confusion matrices of classification between 3 dynamics for the same technique. *DE*, *MA*, *SP*, *ST* and *SD* are détaché, legato, martelé, spiccato, staccato and staccato down respectively and below the accuracies are their corresponding matrices. a) violin b) viola c) cello

From table 6.1 we can see among three instruments, cello has the highest accuracy, which could be explained that players of cello could have a better control of dynamics or have a more clear boundary between piano, mezzo forte and forte. Also, some techniques appear quite different in different instruments. For example, the accuracy of staccato in viola is lower than other techniques while is relatively high in violin and cello.

b) classify between 5 techniques for the same dynamics

	<i>p</i>	<i>mf</i>	<i>f</i>
Avg. Acc.	88.9%	99.3%	95.7%

	<i>DE</i>	<i>ST</i>	<i>SD</i>
<i>DE</i>	99.0%	1.0%	0
<i>ST</i>	0	89.6%	10.4%
<i>SD</i>	0	21.9%	78.1%

	<i>DE</i>	<i>ST</i>	<i>SD</i>
<i>DE</i>	98.0%	1.0%	1.0%
<i>ST</i>	0	100.0%	0
<i>SD</i>	0	0	100.0%

	<i>DE</i>	<i>ST</i>	<i>SD</i>
<i>DE</i>	87.5%	8.3%	4.2%
<i>ST</i>	0	100.0%	0
<i>SD</i>	0	1.0%	99.0%

(a)

	<i>p</i>	<i>mf</i>	<i>f</i>
Avg. Acc.	81.3%	82.1%	89.4%

	<i>DE</i>	<i>MA</i>	<i>SP</i>	<i>ST</i>	<i>SD</i>
<i>DE</i>	92.7%	2.1%	3.1%	0	2.1%
<i>MA</i>	4.2%	90.6%	5.2%	0	0
<i>SP</i>	3.1%	7.3%	85.4%	2.1%	2.1%
<i>ST</i>	1.0%	2.1%	1.0%	53.2%	42.7%
<i>SD</i>	0	0	1.0%	14.6%	84.4%

	<i>DE</i>	<i>MA</i>	<i>SP</i>	<i>ST</i>	<i>SD</i>
<i>DE</i>	89.6%	7.2%	3.1%	0	2.1%
<i>MA</i>	5.2%	91.7%	2.1%	0	1.0%
<i>SP</i>	4.2%	6.2%	84.4%	2.1%	3.1%
<i>ST</i>	0	4.2%	2.1%	72.9%	20.8%
<i>SD</i>	1.0%	2.1%	2.1%	22.9%	71.9%

	<i>DE</i>	<i>MA</i>	<i>SP</i>	<i>ST</i>	<i>SD</i>
<i>DE</i>	92.7%	5.1%	2.1%	0	2.1%
<i>MA</i>	5.2%	90.7%	2.1%	1.0%	1.0%
<i>SP</i>	2.1%	2.1%	91.7%	1.0%	3.1%
<i>ST</i>	1.0%	2.1%	1.0%	53.2%	42.7%
<i>SD</i>	0	0	1.0%	14.6%	84.4%

(b)

	<i>p</i>	<i>mf</i>	<i>f</i>
Avg. Acc.	77.7%	87.3%	77.3%

	<i>DE</i>	<i>MA</i>	<i>SP</i>	<i>ST</i>	<i>SD</i>
<i>DE</i>	87.5%	12.5%	0	0	0
<i>MA</i>	11.5%	87.5%	1.0%	0	0
<i>SP</i>	0	0	80.2%	15.6%	4.2%
<i>ST</i>	0	2.1%	32.3%	48.9%	16.7%
<i>SD</i>	1.0%	0	5.2%	9.4%	84.4%

	<i>DE</i>	<i>MA</i>	<i>SP</i>	<i>ST</i>	<i>SD</i>
<i>DE</i>	86.5%	10.4%	0	0	3.1%
<i>MA</i>	9.4%	88.6%	0	1.0%	1.0%
<i>SP</i>	1.0%	0	85.4%	9.4%	4.2%
<i>ST</i>	0	3.1%	13.6%	83.3%	0
<i>SD</i>	5.2%	1.0%	1.0%	0	92.8%

	<i>DE</i>	<i>MA</i>	<i>SP</i>	<i>ST</i>	<i>SD</i>
<i>DE</i>	86.5%	4.2%	0	1.0%	8.3%
<i>MA</i>	7.3%	91.7%	1.0%	0	0
<i>SP</i>	9.4%	1.0%	74.0%	15.6%	0
<i>ST</i>	2.1%	3.1%	46.9%	43.7%	4.2%
<i>SD</i>	8.3%	0	0	1.0%	90.7%

(c)

Table 6.2: The average accuracies and confusion matrices of classification between 5 techniques for the same dynamics. a) violin b) viola c) cello

From table 6.2 we can see the accuracy of mezzo forte is the highest for violin and cello, and a little bit less than forte in viola, which could be inferred that players could have a better control of technique when playing naturally. The biggest confusion comes between staccato and spiccato which is reasonable as we can see in section 4 that the short strokes of staccato and spiccato are quite similar to each other.

c) classify between any dynamics and techniques

	<i>Violin</i>	<i>Viola</i>	<i>Cello</i>
Avg. Acc.	76.5%	63.6%	73.4%

(a)

		<i>DE (%)</i>			<i>ST (%)</i>			<i>SD (%)</i>		
		<i>p</i>	<i>mf</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>mf</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>mf</i>	<i>f</i>
<i>DE</i>	<i>p</i>	94	4	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
	<i>mf</i>	9	85	5	0	0	1	0	0	0
	<i>f</i>	2	25	71	0	1	1	0	0	0
<i>ST</i>	<i>p</i>	0	0	0	83	0	0	12	5	0
	<i>mf</i>	0	0	0	0	82	8	0	0	10
	<i>f</i>	0	0	0	0	17	83	0	0	0
<i>SD</i>	<i>p</i>	0	0	0	18	0	0	75	6	1
	<i>mf</i>	0	0	0	8	0	0	10	54	28
	<i>f</i>	0	0	0	3	7	0	0	28	62

(b)

		DE (%)			MA (%)			SP (%)			ST (%)			SD (%)		
		<i>p</i>	<i>mf</i>	<i>f</i>												
DE	<i>p</i>	83	9	0	1	1	0	3	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	<i>mf</i>	36	36	6	3	5	9	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
	<i>f</i>	2	26	62	0	1	7	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
MA	<i>p</i>	1	0	0	88	6	1	3	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
	<i>mf</i>	0	3	0	8	71	14	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
	<i>f</i>	0	2	1	0	20	74	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
SP	<i>p</i>	2	0	0	6	0	0	81	4	0	4	1	0	0	1	0
	<i>mf</i>	1	2	0	1	1	4	4	72	13	0	0	0	0	1	1
	<i>f</i>	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	21	72	0	0	0	0	0	5
ST	<i>p</i>	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	49	28	2	14	2	1
	<i>mf</i>	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	14	39	24	3	19	0
	<i>f</i>	0	0	0	2	1	1	0	0	0	2	26	60	0	5	2
SD	<i>p</i>	0	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	20	13	0	57	6	1
	<i>mf</i>	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	4	13	5	6	61	7
	<i>f</i>	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	4	4	7	0	7	25	49

(c)

		DE (%)			MA (%)			SP (%)			ST (%)			SD (%)		
		<i>p</i>	<i>mf</i>	<i>f</i>												
DE	<i>p</i>	65	10	0	17	6	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
	<i>mf</i>	10	68	7	0	6	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	7	0
	<i>f</i>	0	10	78	0	2	3	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	4
MA	<i>p</i>	7	0	0	86	2	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
	<i>mf</i>	13	6	0	4	74	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	<i>f</i>	0	4	5	0	7	82	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
SP	<i>p</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	70	7	1	17	0	0	5	0	0
	<i>mf</i>	1	0	0	7	0	0	7	64	2	10	2	0	4	2	0
	<i>f</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	60	0	7	14	0	6	1
ST	<i>p</i>	0	0	0	1	0	0	14	14	0	57	1	0	14	0	0
	<i>mf</i>	0	0	0	2	0	0	1	9	9	1	77	0	0	0	0
	<i>f</i>	0	0	2	0	1	1	1	0	23	0	2	61	0	2	6
SD	<i>p</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	5	0	14	0	0	77	0	0
	<i>mf</i>	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	91	0
	<i>f</i>	0	0	5	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	92

(d)

Table 6.3: The average accuracies and confusion matrices of classification between any dynamics and techniques. a) average accuracies of three instruments b) confusion matrix of violin c) confusion matrix of viola d) confusion matrix of cello

As expected, the result of this one is a combination of previous two, which can be seen in table 6.3. Although the violin has the highest accuracy, considering the less classes it has than other two instruments, we presume cello has the most distinctive classes.

d) cascade classification between any dynamics and techniques

	<i>Violin</i>	<i>Viola</i>	<i>Cello</i>
Avg. Acc.	71.7%	60.3%	74.9%

(a)

		DE (%)			ST (%)			SD (%)		
		<i>p</i>	<i>mf</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>mf</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>mf</i>	<i>f</i>
DE	<i>p</i>	91	7	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
	<i>mf</i>	6	81	13	0	0	0	0	0	0
	<i>f</i>	1	29	70	0	1	1	16	18	4
ST	<i>p</i>	0	0	0	62	0	0	16	18	4
	<i>mf</i>	0	0	0	0	75	15	0	0	10
	<i>f</i>	0	0	0	0	14	85	0	0	1
SD	<i>p</i>	0	0	0	12	0	0	83	4	1
	<i>mf</i>	0	0	0	6	1	0	13	54	26
	<i>f</i>	0	0	0	8	19	0	1	29	43

(b)

		DE (%)			MA (%)			SP (%)			ST (%)			SD (%)		
		<i>p</i>	<i>mf</i>	<i>f</i>												
DE	<i>p</i>	86	9	2	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	<i>mf</i>	27	34	23	3	5	3	0	2	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
	<i>f</i>	0	39	56	0	2	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
MA	<i>p</i>	3	0	1	82	10	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
	<i>mf</i>	1	1	0	14	63	20	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
	<i>f</i>	0	1	2	0	22	73	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
SP	<i>p</i>	1	0	0	0	0	0	90	6	0	0	2	0	0	1	0
	<i>mf</i>	0	4	1	0	2	2	4	66	20	0	0	0	0	0	1
	<i>f</i>	0	1	4	0	0	1	0	21	72	0	0	0	0	0	1
ST	<i>p</i>	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	57	0	1	27	9	0
	<i>mf</i>	0	0	0	1	1	0	5	2	1	9	31	18	6	24	1
	<i>f</i>	0	0	0	1	3	0	0	6	3	5	26	31	1	11	11
SD	<i>p</i>	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	33	0	0	49	14	2
	<i>mf</i>	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	3	1	2	8	5	7	59	11
	<i>f</i>	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	3	3	1	4	2	8	19	56

(c)

		DE (%)			MA (%)			SP (%)			ST (%)			SD (%)		
		<i>p</i>	<i>mf</i>	<i>f</i>												
DE	<i>p</i>	67	7	0	8	8	0	0	6	1	0	0	0	0	1	0
	<i>mf</i>	11	72	10	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	0
	<i>f</i>	0	17	74	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	5
MA	<i>p</i>	7	0	0	87	4	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	<i>mf</i>	7	7	0	4	74	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	<i>f</i>	0	5	6	0	8	78	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
SP	<i>p</i>	1	0	0	1	0	0	75	9	0	7	1	0	5	0	0
	<i>mf</i>	2	0	0	6	0	0	17	58	3	3	9	0	0	1	0
	<i>f</i>	0	3	0	0	0	1	0	10	46	0	13	22	0	4	1
ST	<i>p</i>	0	0	0	2	0	0	14	16	0	50	1	0	18	0	0
	<i>mf</i>	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	1	4	1	91	0	0	0	0
	<i>f</i>	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	9	0	2	76	0	5	4
SD	<i>p</i>	0	0	0	1	0	0	5	3	0	0	0	0	91	0	0
	<i>mf</i>	1	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	92	1
	<i>f</i>	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	94

(d)

Table 6.4: The average accuracies and confusion matrices of cascade classification between any dynamics and techniques. a) average accuracies of three instruments b) confusion matrix of violin c) confusion matrix of viola d) confusion matrix of cello

Compared to previous one, the accuracy of cascade classification is slightly lower for violin and viola, and slightly higher for cello, which can be seen in table 6.4. We can conclude that the cascade method cannot improve the performance in a salient level.

7. Conclusion

We have proposed a method to analyze and recognize gestures of violin, viola and cello based on gesture data from motion capture system Qualisys. After calibration, bow descriptors computation and score-alignment, each stroke is represented by a vector of bow velocity. We then categorize strokes according to their techniques, dynamics and durations. After analysis of each category, we propose five features to differentiate them. Using LIBSVM and 4-fold cross validation, we perform several classification tasks from different angles to classify them and we have proved that these features are effective.

Future work will mainly focus on investigating other bow descriptors, especially the bow force. Right now we are trying to use regression method to estimate the bow force. However we are having problems when applying models built from calibration data to real data. We will try to solve them and combine bow force with bow velocity to see if it will improve the performance.

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